

COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY: TYPES, SUBJECT MATTER, TASKS, APPROACHES AND CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract. *In this article, one of the important branches of linguistics, typology, or rather, comparative typology, is discussed. Information about the object of study of comparative typology as a science, studied issues, types, approaches and methods is covered.*

Key words: *typology, approaches, branch, comparative, formal and semantic typology.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ТИПОЛОГИЯ: ВИДЫ, ПРЕДМЕТ, ЗАДАЧИ, ПОДХОДЫ И КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается один из важных разделов языкознания, типология, а точнее, сравнительная типология. Освещены сведения об объекте изучения сравнительной типологии как науки, изучаемых вопросах, видах, подходах и методах.*

Ключевые слова: *типология, подходы, отрасль, сравнительная, формально-семантическая типология.*

Typology is a branch of linguistics that deals with the elucidation of the most general patterns of various languages, not necessarily related to each other by a common origin or mutual influence. Typology seeks to identify the most likely occurrences in different languages. If a certain phenomenon is revealed in a representative group of languages, it can be considered a typological pattern applicable to the language as such. Typological analysis can be carried out at the level of sound (phonetic and phonological typology), at the level of words (morphological typology), sentences (syntactic typology) and supra-syntactic structures (typology of text or discourse).

Comparative typology is a significant branch of typology and linguistics that studies languages in comparison with each other in order to establish similarities and differences between languages. Comparison (comparison) of languages can be carried out in historical terms and aim to establish kinship between languages - this approach is represented by comparative historical linguistics, which in the 19th century gave a genealogical classification of languages.

Comparison of languages can also be carried out without taking into account their history and kinship between them - such an approach is represented by comparative typological linguistics, which gave (also in the 19th century) a typological classification of languages.

"Its object is not singular and individual cases of similarity and difference but those which are common for large groups of language elements." [1] "Comparative typology

classifies languages according to their structure.”[4] “Although languages may differ in their material (i.e. have no words of the same root, or common morphemes) their structure (i.e. relations between the elements, functions of the elements) may be similar.

English – Indo European Family – Germanic – Analytic – SVO [5]

Uzbek – Turkic family – Southeastern – Uighur-Chagatai – Agglutinative –SOV”[1]

There are two branches of Comparative Typology: formal and semantic typology.

"Formal typology deals with the units of expression plan of the language which belongs to various levels of language hierarchy. The ultimate goal of Formal typology is identifying formal universals. The major tasks of Formal typology embrace but are not limited to the following: reveal external or formal features of the language; establish common principles of the script, e.g. graphic systems, alphabets, the system of transcription signs, punctuation; establish formal structures of the syllable, composite words and word combinations; establish the formal structure of the sentence etc.

Semantic typology is a branch of Comparative Typology studying the semantic structure of the language and related to the units of content plan. The ultimate goal of Semantic typology is identifying semantic universals which are directly related to the deep structure of the language.

Other issues considered in the frames of Semantic typology are: identifying aims and problems of Semantic typology, defining different semantic fields for comparative analysis, grouping words on the basis of semantic signs, defining semantic fields in different languages, creating criteria to define semantic categories, elaboration of the principles of compiling semantic comparative dictionaries and many others." [2]

Comparative linguistics has its own methods and approaches, just as every discipline has its own methods and approaches. They are comparative, deductive, inductive, statistic, IC (immediate constituents) and transformational methods.

-the comparative method aims at establishing the isomorphic(alongside of allomorphic) features and on their basis the determining of structural types of languages under contrastive investigation:[6]

-the deductive method is based on logical calculation which suggests all the possible variants of realization of a certain feature/phenomenon in speech of one or more contrasted languages;

-the inductive method which needs novarification, since the investigated feature was proved by linguists and therefore the results obtained are possible;

-the statistic method for establishing the necessary quantitative and qualitative representation of some features or for identifying the percentage of co-occurrence of some features or linguistic units in the contrasted languages;

-the IC (immediate constituents) method is employed to contrast only linguistic units for investigating their constituent parts in one or some contrasted languages;

-transformational method for identifying the nature of a linguistic unit in the source language or for determining the difference in the form of expression in the contrasted languages." [3]

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